

Social computing in currency exchange

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Abstract Human communication has evolved over the last decades thanks to rapid technological advances. It has provided us with new ways of communicating with one another and made many aspects of social interaction easier. Social computing is an important area in computer science concerned with the use of computational systems for social purposes. This paper focuses on the use of social computing to simplify the process of currency exchange at airports where services have to be provided to people of all nationalities. This is a complex social scenario in which the buyer and seller must reach an agreement without speaking the same language, in these cases the probability of not understanding all the aspects of the transaction is high. The proposed system improves interaction between users and ensures a fast and secure operation. A Multi-Agent System is the base of the developed software; MAS are an important and commonly used tool in social computing. A case study was conducted with the proposed system at Sydney airport, with a Spanish currency exchange company (Global Exchange) which provides service to travelers from all continents. The Net Promoter Score metric was used to evaluate the developed system and a score of 29.81 was obtained, indicating that customers were highly satisfied with the performance of the system. Moreover, thanks to the system there was an increase of 34% in currency exchange operations and the time it takes to provide service to a customer reduced by 73.67% on average.

Keywords Currency Exchange · Social Computing · Software · Multi-Agent Systems

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1 Introduction

Technology has transformed the way in which we interact with each other. Social networks have become an important element of daily interaction, enabling both personal and professional relationships [3]. However, our communication goes much beyond social networks. Social computing is continually revolutionizing the way in which humans communicate [23].

Social computing is the use of technology for interaction and collaboration between users. In this case, specifically, a computer acts as a tool in the currency exchange process between the teller in an exchange office and a client. The use of technology in communication can bring multiple advantages, however in this proposal its main benefit is to facilitate communication between people, given the characteristics of the environment. Currency exchange is a service that is offered at all airports to people of different nationalities, this service may be difficult if the seller and the buyer cannot communicate in the same language. As communication regards money it is especially important that both parties can clearly understand each other and that the exchange process is carried out in a transparent way. This will help improve customer satisfaction with the provided service. Thus, the business sector can benefit from this paradigm significantly and one aspect that can be improved is currency exchange.

One of the aspects that makes social relations more difficult is the language in which people must interact. When this is different, it is difficult to understand all aspects of a communication in detail. This situation occurs every day in airports, where the transit of people of multiple nationalities (and therefore speakers of multiple languages) far exceeds the percentage of any other environment [24], [11], [33]. In addition, when communication is established to carry out an economic operation, good understanding between both parties is a key aspect. Specifically, one of the activities most frequently carried out between people who speak different languages at airports is an economic operation, the currency exchange [25]. During this currency exchange process there can be a lot of inconveniences such as lack of understanding, possible misunderstandings or the lack of confidence and security that can arise in operations of an economic nature, even other factors can affect the emotional form of making such communication such as waiting time.

It is necessary, therefore, to develop a system that is capable of taking full advantage of the benefits that social computing can offer [13]. Such a system should simplify the communication process between the user and the teller by providing a user-friendly interface for the transaction. Since the system will make all the aspects of the transaction transparent, the teller will know exactly what he or she should do and the client will understand all aspects of the procedure, contributing to their satisfaction with the service. Clients can be attended simultaneously through computers, this will allow the company to attend more clients and to reduce the workload of their employees.

The main contribution of this paper is the development of a system which fulfills the objectives described above. A Multi-Agent System (MAS) was used

in our proposal as it is an important paradigm in social computing [31]. More specifically, a set of agents coordinate and interact with each other in such a way as to guarantee that the environment (in this case, the currency purchase operation) is governed by a set of rules that implies that it is carried out in the appropriate way. The system has been deployed in a real environment (the Sydney airport in Australia) and has been evaluated on the basis of different parameters, such as waiting time for each client or their satisfaction, compared to the traditional care method, where the company's change consultant interacts directly with the client without using any type of technological device for communication.

The rest of the article is structured as follows: the background section 2 analyzes the state of the art in currency exchange systems and section 3 describes the technology and the development of the proposed system. Then the experiment and the results are outlined in section 4. Finally, conclusions are drawn on the users' satisfaction with the proposed system and future work is discussed in section 5.

2 Background

This section outlines the currency exchange companies that operate at present and the way in which they have adapted different technologies to provide their services. We stress however, that none of the companies listed here have used the system proposed in this article. Moreover, this section outlines the legal requirements that currency exchange companies must meet to ensure secure operations and finally, state of art social computing systems are reviewed.

2.1 Existing currency exchange systems

Currency exchange companies are financial institutions whose main function is to buy and sell foreign exchange from different countries. In the past, currency exchange offices were normally located in banks, however their popularity increased due to greater international mobility of people and globalization. As a result, today currency exchange offices can also be found in travel agencies, at airports and other transport hubs.

Although there are no specific statistics regarding the companies that use online as opposed to offline transaction, it is certain that the majority of currency exchange offices opt for offline transactions where all the procedures are carried out by a teller. The procedure followed to exchange money in these entities is fairly simple if the teller and the client can communicate in the same language. The client simply comes to one of these entities to buy a currency which has an exchange rate, and pays a fee for the completion of this exchange process.

Airports are a central place to currency exchange, where clients can usually find a range of companies to choose from. However, upon arrival to another

country many travelers are not aware of the advantages that different companies can offer such as an anti-theft insurance or currency repurchase at the same price. Thus, their choice usually depends on the exchange rates offered by these companies, which tend to be quite even as well as the number of customers queuing up to change their currency. Thus, making the service faster can help a company outperform competition, as it will allow to reduce queues and attract more clients.

Studies like the one presented by Ferris *et al.* in [10] demonstrate that user satisfaction increases considerably when technology is used to provide information of interest. This work in particular provided information on the waiting time that users should expect to wait at a bus stop, however it can be used in the same way to estimate the time a client will wait to change their currency in the office of one company as opposed to its competition. In [1] Allon *et al.* analyze the impact of waiting time on the fast food market rate. This study shows that decreasing the average waiting time by several seconds allows a company to attract more customers. The success of self ordering kiosks has already been demonstrated in similar works, the study presented in [17] looks at the parameters that contribute to their success.

In recent times different business models have been created in an effort to take advantage of the possibilities offered by technology. Within this new model, the following exchange companies stand out:

- American Express [5]. American Express Company, commonly known as Amex or AmEx, is a New York-based financial institution with more than 1,700 offices in over 130 countries. Fortune magazine ranks it 95th in the world ranking of the world's largest companies. In addition to currency exchange, its services include credit cards, traveler's checks, insurance, stock exchange services and online banking, the latter two supervised by American Express Bank.
- Travelex [16]. Travelex Group is a foreign exchange firm founded in London in 1976. Travelex is a global currency exchange specialist that provides payment and receipt of domestic and international funds for companies of all sizes, besides of bureaux de change and issuing prepaid credit cards for use by travelers. It is the world's largest foreign exchange bureau [18], operates in 27 countries and has more than 1,500 stores. Each year, Travelex processes payments worldwide for more than 35,000 companies to one million beneficiaries.
- Global Exchange [9]. Global Exchange is the world's third largest company specializing in providing currency exchange services to the tourist public at international airports and other popular tourist destinations. At present, it has a network of more than 150 offices located in 46 international airports in 21 countries and 4 continents, with a staff of more than 2,200 employees who serve 4 million customers each year. Among its innovations are its services for online currency reservation with home delivery or airport pick-up, as well as the currency exchange service for managers and employees of companies.

Table 1 Services offered by existing currency exchange companies.

	Services to users		Services to business
	Reverse	Home delivery	International transactions
American Express			X
Travelex	X	X	X
Global Exchange	X	X	X
Ebury			X
Kantox			X
ExactChange	X	X	X
Money Exchange		X	

- Ebury [19]. Ebury is a company specializing in Forex services that combines geographic expansion with constant product innovation and proprietary technology. Ebury serves more than 5,000 European companies and has a team of more than 260 employees that support exporting and importing companies, under the standards of payment security and agility of transactions from Europe to any other destination in the world, thanks to an offer of more than 140 currencies.
- Kantox [20]. Its functions include access to mid-market exchange rates, updated in real time, creation of exchange rate alerts, multi-user and multi-company accounts, a detailed FX control panel and uninterrupted access to the platform. Instead of trading through a bank or broker, Kantox enables two trusted companies to exchange currencies directly, in peer-to-peer mode.
- ExactChange [21]. Exact Change, is a payment institution expert in full forex services, operating in the market since 1989. They specialise in foreign retail banknote buying and selling, foreign currency sales, international payments to current accounts, person-to-person money transfers without the need for a bank account, payment account management and wholesale buying and selling of foreign banknotes, carrying out more than 34,000 transactions per month.
- Money Exchange [22]. Money Exchange has experience in sending and receiving international transfers for almost 20 years. It has an extensive network of offices and agents that allows us to cover the entire national territory. The international division is established in the main European countries. Its main innovation is the sending of money at home and even to other countries.

Analyzing the platforms and technologies that the main companies currently use, we can observe how most of them focus on certain common operations: i) the purchase and reservation of currency; ii) the sending of currency at home; iii) international transactions. Table 1 shows a summary of the main services offered by these companies.

Although some companies have used the Internet to provide services to users that enable them to buy currency or book money online, none have provided solutions to customers at airports who tend to be in a hurry and need a

fast service. For this reason, it is necessary to develop a self-ordering kiosk system (Fig. 1) that simplifies the process of currency exchange in airport offices. Thus, the system proposed in this work is an advancement over traditional currency exchange offices, which can have a very positive impact on customer satisfaction.

Fig. 1 Proposed case study.

2.2 Safety in currency exchange

In this type of system, unambiguous user identification is necessary for many reasons. Currency exchange operations usually use traditional means of identification (passports, identity documents, identity cards or any other valid traditional method of identification). However, this method of identification may not always be accurate and safe, additional information on the identity of clients could be obtained by means of technology. To this end, the aim is to: i) analyze national and international databases for the identification of persons; ii) detect patterns of criminal behavior, the movement of large sums of money in different countries, the use of false identity and different credit cards, etc.; iii) identification of Politically Exposed Persons (PEP) or those that appear on criminal records.

2.3 Social computing

The Internet also introduced a social element that allows the users to collaborate, share interests, publish personal insights and use the computers in a social way. Some authors approach social computing as the computational facilitation for social studies and human social dynamics as well as the design

and use of new technologies that consider social context. In 1994, Schuler defined social computing as the methodology “describing any type of computing application in which software serves as an intermediary or a focus for a social relation” [28]. So social computing is basically the use of computers for social purposes [4]. In social computing, the Internet supports the infrastructures within which social interactions and problem-solving activities will be performed according to the deeply interactive rules and patterns that regulate societies. Key aspects include end user experience in interacting with a social machine and user perception [31].

For Robertson et al. [26] the power of social computing resides in the programmable combination of contributions from both humans and computers. On the one hand, within organized social computation workflows, humans bring their competences, knowledge and skills, together with their networks of social relationships and their understanding of social structures. On the other hand, new technologies can search for and deliver relevant information. Humans can then use this information within their contexts to achieve their goals and, eventually, to improve the overall environment in which they live. Social Computing has evolved during recent years to provide more realistic ways to improve social behaviors and relationships using computer science.

Current solutions have focused on theoretical underpinnings, technological infrastructure and applications [26]. These range from simple forms of social interaction to the coordination of large-scale collaborative efforts, and it is necessary to provide new solutions for: various forms of socially-distributed problem-solving; various aspects of social relationship management and various aspects of social cognition or social sense-making (for example, people’s perception of an economic or social transaction, social networks or currency exchange)

In the business sector, the use of the Internet has brought innovation in the form of social networks which facilitate contact between users and businesses [29]. This makes it possible to provide advertising and online sales services in a more direct way, due to the large amount of personal information provided by users. Existing social networks focus primarily on facilitating social networking mechanisms, but do not attempt to respond to complex problems. Troubleshooting with a high level of complexity requires the design of new computing platforms and the use of innovative technologies that allow for the inclusion of organizational aspects and distributed problem-solving mechanisms [31], [12].

Up until now we have focused on social computing as a methodology that is closely linked to social networks however it goes much further than that. Social computing is the basis of the latest trends in software system research and development. Research works that focus on the social interaction of the elements in a system have proliferated [7]. This is the case of the most current lines of research on MAS related to automatic negotiation, argumentation, trust, reputation, etc. Also, the management of virtual organizations [27] (which make it possible to implement a social network in any hierarchical structure), or social learning [2] or agreement technologies (which have evolved from being

an area of general study of philosophy, sociology and human sciences, to being a key term used by many countries in different lines of research on MAS).

Social networks like Facebook and Twitter have acquired great importance in the field of social computing. Although initially they were not conceived as such, they have come to be the first versions of social machines, this is because apart of their main function as social networks they can also help solve social problems. Thus, in the field of conventional computing we can find: i) social machines oriented at the creation of climatological models (which require large computational resources and management of large volumes of data, but in which the social aspect is not very significant) [8]; ii) social machines for air traffic control (in which high levels of computing and data management are required and in which the social aspect has only recently been recognized as important) [30]; iii) social machines based on Crowdsourcing (like GalaxyZoo, with social, computational and low data management levels) [8]; iv) social machines based on collaborative content creation (like Wikipedia, which has a considerable level of social interaction but where information management and computational complexities are low) and machines that focus on (v) social relationships (like Facebook which has a high degree of social complexity).

The design of social machines with these characteristics requires research on the use of distributed artificial intelligence, which allows to model both social behaviors and the interaction and organizational structures found in human societies. In this respect, MAS are particularly suitable for the creation and management of artificial societies.

2.4 Using Multi-agent systems in Social Computing

MAS incorporates capabilities that include autonomy, reactivity, pro-activity, learning [15], as well as ubiquitous, distributed and somewhat intelligent communication among its elements. Their characteristics cover a large part of the requirements posed by this project, in which it is necessary to adapt to the needs of users in a ubiquitous, autonomous and dynamic way to carry out the process of currency exchange safely and through different channels in an optimal way.

In a MAS, the data is organized in a distributed way and there is no global control system. Thus, each agent focuses on their own conduct, is guided by their objectives when taking initiative and decides dynamically on the tasks assigned to other agents. To achieve the overall objectives of the system it is necessary for actors to work in a coordinated way, mainly through negotiation mechanisms.

An aspect of special interest for this project is the construction of a platform that makes it possible to model organizational aspects and mechanisms for dynamic re-organization. To design such a platform it is necessary to look into the particular characteristics of MAS. MAS can be classified as open or closed. The fundamental difference between the two is that a closed MAS is created with a fixed structure and objectives, while in an open system agents

can enter or exit the system dynamically and its objectives can change. The aim of this system is to design an open systems. Open systems provide dynamic operating environments, where new components are integrated or existing components leave the system continuously, and where the operating conditions themselves can change unpredictably.

Open systems are characterized by heterogeneity of participants, limited confidence, conflicting individual objectives and a high probability of non-conformity with specifications [32], [14]. The main function of an agent platform is to provide an implementation framework for the agents that are part of it. The design and construction of agents and their subsequent behaviour depend not only on their internal architecture but also on the agent platform in which they are implemented. The platforms that were designed a few years ago focused on the design of the agents participating in the system, thus they could not be applied directly to an open MAS where the participants in the system are not known a priori.

An organization in the computational environment, more specifically in that of a MAS, is used to describe a group of agents that coordinate through a series of behavior patterns and the establishment of roles to achieve the system's objectives.

A MAS model must be able to define organizations that can be dynamically adapted to changes in the environment or in the organization's specification. Dynamic adaptation means that the structure and behavior of a MAS can change while it is being executed, without disturbing its performance. These changes include the addition, deletion, or replacement of components [6].

Agent organizations follow the same principles as human organizations. Within an organization, specific agents are assigned different tasks in order to achieve a series of defined global objectives.

The characteristics that MAS provide are very suitable for the development of solutions for the currency exchange market, where agents can be classified by currency type, country, office etc. In this way, the system can clearly identify different customer profiles and learn from them in order to establish currency prices or promotions. This will also allow the company to optimally adjust its profit margin.

3 Proposed system

This project has been designed in collaboration with an international currency exchange company, called Global Exchange. Global Exchange has a new affiliate in Sydney Airport, Australia, with around 150 employees of which 80 per cent are bilingual and 40 per cent speak a third language. However, this is not enough to be able to communicate with each client using his/her native language. The main aim of this project is to provide a system that will help eliminate all possible language barriers in providing currency exchange service, reducing errors in communication and the time of service.

To develop the proposed system, the needs of the market have been analysed and the new possibilities that technology gives us to provide for these needs have been considered. The aim was to design a system that would allow to exchange currency at airports in an easy and quick way. The main objective of the system is to provide a safe and error-free operation process in human-to-human interaction, thanks to the advantages of human-machine interaction in social computing. Secondly, the aim is to reduce the time that a teller needs to attend each customer, which considerably reduces the time that clients have to wait for the service, this increases their satisfaction with the service. Rapid service and clear communication is important as clients often have little time to exchange the currency before their flight leaves.

All the developed functionalities will be integrated in a tablet which will be located in each of the offices in the airport. To this end, the following functional objectives must be met:

i) Interconnection with central systems: it is important that all information introduced in the device remains up-to-date and unified with the company's central information systems, this will ensure that transactions are recorded properly and that the exchange rate is appropriate. Since most airports are not allowed to deploy a Wi-Fi access point, the interconnection must be via cable;

ii) Interconnection with money laundering and terrorism prevention systems: the system will be integrated with existing blacklisting services;

iii) Multilanguage: as mentioned above, one of the main problems in providing currency exchange service to people of all nationalities is the difficulty in communication. When one of the two parties does not have a good command of the language in which the conversation takes place, it is likely that errors or misunderstandings occur. To resolve this problem, the system will offer a wide variety of languages so that users can be attended in their native language or in the one they know best;

iv) Presentation of offers: the rate at which the service is provided often depends on the amount of money that a client wants to exchange. Generally, the more money the customer exchanges, the lower the exchange rate. In order to do this, sections are defined with each type of fee and presented to the user so that he or she can decide carefully which is the option that best adapts to their needs, without feeling pressured by the advisor of the window as he or she could pass until now;

v) User verification: To verify a client, a confirmation request must be sent to the client's email. In the traditional currency exchange method the client spells out their email address to the teller, this increases the probability of typing errors, implying difficulties in user verification. In the proposed system the user introduces their e-mail address by themselves in order to avoid typing mistakes.

vi) Payment management in the device: the user can choose to pay with their credit card and will only have to give the receipt to the teller at the counter, whose task will be to verify that the personal information has been entered correctly and will subsequently give the client the corresponding amount

of money in the currency they had requested. This makes the whole procedure much faster. If the customer wants to pay with cash, the advisor will issue the receipt. In this case, the process of buying and selling is also much more simple as all the information is introduced in the tablet and there is no need for the client to communicate anything to the teller;

vii) Feedback: the system will be fed back with the information obtained from the transactions. In this way, it will learn about different user profiles, providing offers that are of interest to users.

The company will pursue the following objectives:

i) Reduced time of service: the use of social computing in the process of currency exchange implies a reduction in the time that tellers spend at attending the clients. This is because a large part of the process is carried out by client through the device.

ii) Reduced waiting time: as a result of the above objective, clients will not have to wait for long to be attended. In addition, several clients will be able to make their currency exchange requests simultaneously, on the tablets provided in the office. The cost of supplying the office with additional tablets is not high and can reduce the waiting time considerably. This also reduces the company's needs for more staff members.

Fig. 2 Software diagram.

iii) More operations: by reducing the time required to attend each client and by providing digital simultaneous service, it will be possible to offer the service to more clients. Reduced queues are likely to attract more clients, given that the majority of them are in a hurry to get to their flight on time.

iv) Error free data: social computing greatly enhances the process of communication between people who do not speak the same language. In this case, the user is responsible for providing their information electronically, reducing the possibility of errors occurring due to poor understanding of a language.

v) Offers suited to users interests: social computing and agent technology are integrated in the system. This makes it possible for the system to detect and learn from behavior patterns, creating profiles of the clients and matching the offers they are interested in. These learning capabilities allow the system to provide users with offers that are suited to their interests, such offers will persuade users to increase the amount of money that users exchange.

Fig. 3 Agents communication diagram.

Part of the designed software, more specifically the one that customers interact with, runs on a tablet with an Android operating system. This device was chosen because it provides greater flexibility in connecting peripheral devices. In this case, the device must be connected i) physically to an access point via Ethernet cable connected to an adapter and the USB of the Android device; and ii) through Bluetooth to the devices in charge of the transaction (band, chip and contactless card reader) and a receipt printer. The software was designed in modules (see diagram in Fig. 2), this type of systems are dynamic and can add new solutions at any of the modules without interfering with the operation of the rest. To ensure that the immediate implementation of solutions is secure a main app was created to execute the agent in charge of controlling the flow of the transaction: calculation and presentation of the price of currency, data collection, providing private promotions based on the customer's data so that they fit the profile, payment management (which allows payment by card at the moment or cash at the counter) and printing of the transaction receipt.

Each functional block is structured in agents, which are embedded in different applications, so that a functional change in one part of the system does not affect the rest of the modules that operate within the system. Fig. 3 shows the connectivity between the different agents and Fig. 4 shows a sequence diagram of an error-free operation (to simplify its understanding).

Fig. 4 Agents sequence diagram.

Thus, each module has an associated app where an agent is executed to ensure that the associated standards its functionality is complied with at all times depending on the state of the environment: the entire operation. These modules have a completely independent application that encapsulates all its functionality and communicates with the application through Android Interface Definition Language (AIDL). In this way, the main application relinquishes control of functionality to the secondary application, which will perform its operations and return the result and control to the main application. Thus, there is an interface that provides independence even when working with other SDKs (Software Development Kits), such as the payment gateway system or with specific protocols, such as the ticket printing device. In this way, if a better system appears in the future, it can be integrated transparently. Each of the system's independent modules is presented in greater detail below.

- Currency exchange fee: this module presents the user with the fees the company will charge for exchanging currency, these fees vary depending on the currency and the private algorithm of the company. These prices are calculated specifically for each office and include factors such as the profit margin, the minimum value at which each currency is traded, etc. In addition, the user has the option of choosing different fees, depending on the quantity they want to exchange, in this way the user can choose the offer that they find most convenient. The agent who is in charge of the fee system must guarantee the client that the following rules will be met: i) the fee does not change once the client has selected it and completes the transaction (if this is not possible the transaction is stopped by the system and fee information is recalculated). ii) the stated monetary value can be provided based on the minimum value at which the office operates. If this is not the case, the lower and upper rounding should be suggested so that the office can operate so that the user chooses whichever rounding he or she wishes; iii) the office has sufficient cash to satisfy the amount requested by the user.
- Blacklist: this module connects to different blacklisting services in multiple countries, they contain information on potential tax evaders, criminals etc. These blacklists were examined to ensure that they comply with the law in terms of the company's own operations: it is guaranteed that the maximum amount of change is not exceeded, that no two operations take place in distant locations in a short period of time. In this case, the agent responsible for ensuring the viability of the operation must check that the following rules are met: i) the data provided by the user are not included in any of the databases. If so, the transaction is permitted, but the teller is warned, who will act as required depending on the type of list; ii) the user has not reached the maximum exchangeable currency under the laws of his or her home country and the country in which the transaction is carried out; iii) the user has not conducted transactions with the company that violate the law in the past; iv) the user has not changed currency with the company in distant places in a sufficiently short period of time to be unfeasible for its location in both offices.
- Promotions: in order to foster loyalty among customers who have previously changed currency at any of the company's offices, private promotions can be presented to users. In the same way, depending on different circumstances, private promotions can be presented even if the client is new. In this case, the agent must ensure that the following rules are met: i) the promotions presented are not exclusive of any other factor related to the transaction, such as the selection of a special price tranche. In the event that a promotion is exclusive, it is not shown to the user; ii) the customer complies with the conditions of the promotion in terms of sometimes usage, etc. If the customer does not comply with the conditions, the promotion is not shown to the user.
- Payment: this module of the system connects to the payment gateway which, for the moment, is an external system of the company. In order not

to remain permanently linked to a system and be able to change payment gateway in the future, this application allows the use of different SDKs, even changing gateway depending on each country. Initially, SumUp was used in this first prototype, from SumUp Payments Ltd. which allows payments by card with chip, band and contactless. In this case, the trader must check that the following rules are met: i) the exchange rate has not changed since the confirmation of the purchase in the step carried out by the first trader involved in the transaction. In the event that the price has changed, the exchange rate, the amount to be paid, the rules of the agents associated with the above steps are updated, and a confirmation message is displayed to the user; ii) if the user chooses card payment, the transaction must return a successful message. If the system returns an error message, the customer will be asked to pay a total of three times and if all failed, the customer will be prompted to pay at the counter.

- Printer: there are different hardware devices and protocols that allow the printing of tickets through USB, Bluetooth or Wi-Fi connections. In our case, for this first system we have chosen the Bluetooth option to reduce the physical connection and the ESC/POS protocol, a variation of the Epson Standard Code for Printers (ESC/P), created by the company Epson for communication with its printers and which is the most used standard for communication with ticket printing devices. It supports the printing of images, being able to include the company logo on the ticket itself and a QR code that identifies the transaction unambiguously, so that the advisor of the window only has to read the QR and will load on the computer all information regarding the operation that has made the user. The associated agent must check that the following rules are met: i) the printer is connected to the tablet, with the device initially chosen, through Bluetooth; ii) the system returns the return code successfully, otherwise, the transaction identifier is displayed on screen, which the user must point to present at the window.

The advantage of designing the system by orienting it to agents is that each agent or layer of agents that form a module can be replaced by another agent or group of agents with a different way to achieve the objectives. This allows each module to operate completely independently, allowing the system to work with different hardware components or service provider systems in a transparent way for the whole system. Fig. 5 shows a diagram of how the software works on the tablet.

4 Case study

To validate whether the proposed system provides more benefits than the traditional method of currency exchange, it was necessary to conduct a case study in which its performance would be compared with different control groups. This subsection describes the implementation of the proposed system in detail.

Fig. 5 Software system schema.

4.1 Experimental set-up

The experiment was divided into two phases and took place between August and November 2017. In the first phase, the tellers participating in the case study did their work as usual, using the traditional face-to-face currency exchange method. In the second phase of the experiment, the proposed system was implemented and the tellers used it to provide service to the clients at the airport.

The first phase of the experiment was conducted in August and September, in this phase all the objective parameters to be improved through the use of the system have been checked and measured. The start time of each currency exchange operation was done through the monitoring system used by the security cameras. At the end of this stage, a process was carried out to compile the values (some of them manually) of the objective factors: persons for each age range, nationality, operation time, amount of transactions, amount per transaction, acceptance of suggested offers and errors in the obtained user data. The system was implemented in the second phase, in the months of October and November. Operation time was measured from the time the customer started interacting with the tablet, nationality and age range information were obtained from the passport. The system also shows an analysis of the amount per transaction and number of transactions performed per day, week and month (and for different time slots within a day) as well as the percentage of acceptance of suggested offers and errors in the obtained user data.

Table 2 Case study participants classified by their nationality and age range.

	25 - 30	30 - 35	35 - 40	40 - 45	45 - 50	50 - 55	Total
Argentinian (ARS)	65	85	87	90	82	84	493
Brazil (BRL)	76	103	102	140	96	78	595
China (RMB)	53	68	172	135	82	27	537
Colombia (COP)	25	34	30	44	52	49	234
Germany (EUR)	37	26	47	85	111	34	340
India (INR)	54	82	67	79	98	56	436
Japan (JPY)	45	132	139	106	72	3	497
Korea (KRW)	38	108	130	149	56	21	502
Mexico (MXN)	64	75	110	80	67	44	440
New Zealand (NZD)	68	99	145	167	102	131	712
Qatar (QAR)	0	12	2	21	7	0	42
Spain (EUR)	2	35	35	66	57	0	195
United Kingdom (GBP)	17	16	71	96	34	18	252
United States (USD)	35	34	86	133	65	64	417
Total	579	909	1,223	1,391	981	609	5,692

The assessment was conducted at T1 Sydney Kingford Smith International Airport, Sydney, Australia. Sydney Kingford Smith International Airport receives forty million passengers annually, of which fourteen million are international. Global Exchange was conceded all 21 currency exchange offices at Sydney airport's international terminal, each office has 12 Self Service Kiosks and six tellers exchanging currency at the counter, if the currency exchange has been performed at the Self Service Kiosk the teller only verifies if personal information has been entered correctly and exchanges the currency.

Over the course of the case study, 5,692 people aged between 25 and 55 used the service to exchange the currency from their country of origin to AUD or vice versa. Table 2 classifies the case study participants by their nationality and age range.

4.2 Results

The different factors measured in the case study were evaluated in order to obtain the results. The performance of the implemented system was assessed by looking at the extent to which it helped improve these variables. The first part of this section analyses customer satisfaction with the proposed currency exchange system. Then, the parameters collected in the case study are compared: the time it took to attend a client using the traditional method and the time of operation with the proposed system; the amount of transactions and amount of money exchanged before and after the implementation of the proposed system. Differences in obtaining data from customers have also been studied.

The performance of the proposed system was assessed by comparing it with the traditional money exchange method, which had been used by the company (decrease in the time of operation/increase in the amount of transactions per day/increase in the amount of currency exchanged/customer loyalty/percentage of acceptance of offers/decrease in error in process of obtaining user data). The conducted case study consist of two phases because we could

not compare our system with that of competing companies. This was not possible because it would have been necessary to define the same parameters and the same users, so it would not have been a valid test. Another aspect that prevents such is the confidentiality of this type of transactions, since no competitor would provide personal user information and transaction data (nationality, age, amount of currency exchanged, etc.). Moreover, all currency exchange offices at Sydney airport are owned by Global Exchange.

As we can see in Fig. 6 there has been an improvement in the variables evaluated (Amount per transaction, Customer satisfaction, Obtaining of User Data, Operation Time, Transaction Volume) for customers from Asian countries. Obtaining of User Data and Customer Satisfaction are the variables that achieved the best rating, Global Exchange also considers these variables the most important since their aim is to satisfy customers and be able to provide them with new offers. A large percentage of these customers will return to the company to perform another exchange operation.

Fig. 6 Comparison of the average values given by customers according to their nationality for the factors analysed.

The following subsections discuss more factors that were evaluated as part of the case study.

4.2.1 Customer satisfaction

In order to assess user satisfaction with the system, a feedback system was implemented over the two-month case study period. The feedback system asked the user for two different ratings. One regarding the exchange rate, something that users generally do not find pleasing. The other rating was on the exchange procedure provided by the developed system. Here, we only focused on the ratings that regarded the performance of the implemented system. If a user liked the procedure then they will not hesitate to recommend its use to others. As one of the objectives is to make the currency exchange process simple and user-friendly, customers can even recommend this system to their acquaintances, the Net Promoter Score (NPS) metric was used to evaluate user satisfaction with the system.

NPS provides a metric that is used to measure customer satisfaction through the question “How likely is it that you would recommend our company/product/service to a friend or colleague?”. In our case, the question is “Would you recommend using a kiosk like this to a friend or colleague for their money exchange operations?”. In NPS, users who respond with a score of 9 to 10 are the “Promoters”. Users who respond with a score of 0 to 6 are labeled “Detractors”. Responses of 7 and 8 are labeled “Passives”. Then, NPS is calculated by subtracting the percentage of users who are “Detractors” from the percentage of users who are “Promoters” by applying the equation defined in (1).

$$NPS = \frac{Promoters * 100}{TotalRespondents} - \frac{Detractors * 100}{TotalRespondents} \quad (1)$$

So NPS can be as low as -100 if all the users are “Detractors” or as high as $+100$ if all users are “Promoters”. In general, an NPS that is positive is good enough and an NPS of $+50$ is excellent.

Would you recommend using a kiosk like this to a friend or colleague for their money exchange operations?

0 never - 10 always

Fig. 7 Feedback form.

All the 5,692 users filled the form shown in Fig. 7. 2,201 of them were “Promoters”, 2,979 were “Passive” and 504 were “Detractors”, resulting in a value of $NPS = 29.81$, which is considered an intermediate level among good ($NPS > 0$) and excellent ($NPS \geq 50$) results.

Table 3 Feedback results.

Total clients	Promoters	Passive	Detractors
5,692	2,201	2,979	504

4.2.2 Operation time

The average that tellers spend at providing service to each client reduced significantly, from 319 seconds (without using the system) to 84 seconds (with the system). This reduction is due to the fact that the teller only performs a half of the procedure: they receive the receipt of the currency purchase process, which specifies the amount of currency that the customer is to receive and the currency with which he is making the purchase. Moreover, the time a client waits from the moment they queue until they are attended reduced from 276 seconds to just 128 seconds. A comparison between these times in the two phases is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Operation and queuing time comparison.

4.2.3 More transactions and greater amounts of money

The amount of completed transactions increased by 27%, this is due to the number of customers who were previously discouraged from exchanging currency when they saw a large number of people queued for the service. Customers from Asian countries knew of the implementation of the system, this had also contributed to an increase of customers. For privacy reasons the amount of daily, weekly or monthly transactions cannot be disclosed.

As for the increase in foreign exchange, there was a 34% increase per transaction. This was mainly due to the fact that by showing three options with which to obtain a better exchange rate, people increased the amount of money they exchanged in order to get the offer that benefited them. However, the company cannot reveal the daily, weekly or monthly amount of transactions.

4.2.4 Obtaining user data

The main aspects that were considered in the evaluation of the proposed system were the waiting time period per customer and the extent of customer satisfaction in interacting with the designed system. However, for an international company like Global Exchange, it is very important to have detailed

information on its customers (mainly the nationality and age range of the customer), which is provided by the developed system. This will allow the company's marketing team to develop an operational strategy for currency exchange offers with this target audience in mind. This allows marketing campaigns to focus on building loyalty in a specific market niche and to focus on attracting customers with other features that do not change currency through the system.

Another noteworthy figure was the percentage of users who gave up their email addresses, the percentage of users who gave up their email addresses in the first phase was around 23.15% and the percentage of users who gave up their email addresses in the second phase was 84.3%. Of the mails that were provided in the first phase, 11.7% of the mails were erroneous (a reply was received from the mail server informing about it), while in the second phase, this percentage was reduced to 5.52% (Fig. 9.)

Fig. 9 Gathered emails comparison.

In this case, the number of customers operating is not too significant since the company is the only one operating at the airport as it has the exclusive concession of currency exchange. However, it has been evaluated since there are a number of potential customers who change currency outside the airport (at their travel destination or at exchange offices in the city centre), noting an increase in the number of customers.

5 Conclusions and future work

The results of the case study demonstrate that the objectives posed in this work have been achieved. Our main goal was to boost the company's performance by making its services faster. This could be achieved by pursuing multiple sub-objectives. The use of a multi-language system made it possible to provide service to a wide range of clients coming from different countries. This made it possible to provide good service to people whose native language was not known by the tellers (such as Asian or Oriental languages). Short waiting period for the service also encouraged customers to change their currency in the company's office, before going to their destination. Notable data on system usage have been obtained; the operation time and the queue time. The time it took to exchange currency decreased by 73.67%, that was around 235 seconds less for an average operation. The waiting time in the queue was reduced by 148 seconds, resulting in an average of 53.62%. These percentages show why the system obtained such a good NPS value.

Due to the success of the first version of the prototype, future work will focus on the design of a new version which will integrate all the peripheral devices in a single device (printer, card reader) together with the tablet. The aim of this new version will be to attract new customers with a more visible and appealing design. Once the new device with all the integrated components has been developed, it will be deployed in the company's offices at airports around the world. After an evaluation period of four months, the system will be re-evaluated in this case, taking into account airports where there are offices of rival companies, so that there may be a wider scope for attracting customers. This also allows knowing other data and cross-checking them with data from the counters of other airports to know, improve and adapt the products to the customer, improving the user's attention and experience with the system.

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